

Catalytic Waves of β -Mercapto-Propionic Acid at the Dropping Mercury Electrode

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The polarographic behaviour of β -mercapto-propionic acid (MPA) at the dropping mercury electrode, investigated in ammoniacal cobaltous solution evince the occurrence of catalytic hydrogen wave ($E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ 1.55); the shape and height of which was found to be influenced by the concentration of buffer constituents and by the presence of the surface active substances and salts. The height of the catalytic wave was found to be independent of mercury pressure, although, it varies linearly with the concentration of MPA ($1.0 \times 10^{-4} M - 3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$). Catalytic hydrogen wave can, therefore, be successfully utilised for the quantitative determination of MPA down to $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$. In the presence of cobaltic ion, however, MPA does not yield catalytic wave.

The electrochemical behaviour of the physiologically important sulphhydryl compounds at the dropping mercury electrode has been the subject of considerable interest during the past few years¹⁻⁵. The compounds containing -SH and disulphide (-SS) groups have been known to produce (1) the anodic waves corresponding to the formation of insoluble or complex mercury salt, (2) the cathodic waves corresponding to the reduction of -SS form and (3) the catalytic waves. Traces of cysteine⁶⁻⁷, cystine⁸, proteins⁹ and some thio acids and their disulphides¹⁰ have been reported to give rise to typical catalytic hydrogen waves in ammoniacal cobalt or nickel solutions, which are very important for a sensitive analytical determination. The various theories propounded by several workers on the cobalt catalysed hydrogen waves given by a sulphhydryl compounds have been reviewed by Mairanovskii¹¹. In view of the great biological significance of the catalytic waves produced by sulphhydryl compounds it was considered of interest to study the system cobalt- β -mercapto-propionic acid (referred to herein as MPA) in ammoniacal medium polarographically with the aim of obtaining new experimental results concerning the catalytic reaction of MPA and possibilities of its determination at lower concentrations, for which, however, no reference could be traced out in the literature.

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EXPERIMENTAL

β -mercapto propionic acid (99.1%, Evan's Chemetics, Inc., New York) and Anal-R (B.D.H.) reagents NH_4OH , NH_4Cl , CoCl_2 , KNO_3 , etc., were used and their solutions prepared in doubly distilled air-free conductivity water.

Polarographic curves were recorded manually by a Cambridge (General purpose) polarograph, using a thermostated polarographic H-cell. An external saturated calomel electrode connected to the cell by means of an agar bridge, served as a reference electrode. The capillary having the following characteristic $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 1.801 \text{ mg}^{2/3}\text{sec}^{-1/6}$ was used. Dissolved air was removed from the solution by bubbling oxygen free nitrogen through the cell and passing it over the solution during the electrolysis. The necessary correction was made for residual current in determining diffusion current data. To prevent the air oxidation of cobaltous-ammonia complex to the cobaltic state, the cobalt solution was added to the air-free ammonia buffer under nitrogen atmosphere.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our previous communication¹² in this series has dealt with the polarographic behaviour of MPA at the dropping mercury electrode in 0.1 M KCl and 0.005% Triton X-100; which reveal that MPA produces a well defined reversible anodic wave (between pH 2.5-7.90)

Fig. 1. Polarographic waves of 1.5 M $(\text{NH}_3 + \text{NH}_4\text{Cl})$ in the presence and absence of Co^{2+} and MPA.

Curve-1. 1.5 M $(\text{NH}_3 + \text{NH}_4\text{Cl})$ alone.

Curve-2. 1.5 M $(\text{NH}_3 + \text{NH}_4\text{Cl}) + 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M CoCl}_2$.

Curve-3. 1.5 M $(\text{NH}_3 + \text{NH}_4\text{Cl}) + 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M MPA}$.

Curve-4. 1.5 M $(\text{NH}_3 + \text{NH}_4\text{Cl}) + 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M CoCl}_2 + 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M MPA}$.

Curve-5. 1.5 M $(\text{NH}_3 + \text{NH}_4\text{Cl}) + 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M CoCl}_2 + 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M MPA}$ (air oxidised).

involving one electron transfer process and ill defined waves at higher pH values. It has been proved mathematically and experimentally that the anodic wave of MPA does not correspond to the formation of a dimer but rather to the formation of mercury compound $RSHg$ (MPA being represented as RSH) in accordance with the equation

On the other hand, preliminary experiments showed that in ammonia-ammonium chloride buffer, MPA does not give anodic wave (Fig. 1, curve 1) but leads to some interesting phenomenon. Figure 1 represents a set of the polarographic curves of $1.5M$ $(NH_3 + NH_4Cl)$ buffer in the presence of $CoCl_2$ and MPA. In the absence of MPA, the only one wave due to the reduction of Co^{2+} occurred (curve 2). However, the simultaneous presence of $CoCl_2$ and MPA was manifested by two waves (curve 4), the I is due to the reduction of cobalt and wave II, the half wave potential of which corresponds, neither to cobalt nor to MPA occurred at about 0.2 volts more positive than the wave of ammonium ion alone (curve 1). Brdicka and Heyrovsky have also reported such typical waves for cystein and proteins respectively, as the waves due to hydrogen catalysed by the presence of cysteine and proteins. The influence of the various factors viz., the concentration of buffer constituents, MPA concentration, surface active substances, Hg-pressure etc., have been studied as under.

Effect of ammonia-ammonium chloride concentration : The effect of varying concentrations of buffer constituents i.e., NH_3 and NH_4Cl has been shown in Figure 2, which represents the polarographic curves of MPA and $CoCl_2$ both $10^{-3}M$, in different concentrations of the

Fig. 2. Polarographic waves of MPA and $CoCl_2$ both $10^{-3}M$, in varying concentrations of $(NH_3 + NH_4Cl)$ buffer.

The concentration of $(NH_3 + NH_4Cl)$ buffer was (1) $0.1M$, (2) $0.5M$, (3) $1.0M$, (4) $1.5M$ and (5) $2.0M$.

NH_3 and NH_4Cl buffer. It may be seen that MPA does not yield any catalytic wave in the presence of $0.1M$ $(NH_3 + NH_4Cl)$ (curve 1). However, in $0.5M$ $(NH_3 + NH_4Cl)$, a very small wave is obtained (curve 2), whose height increases with the increasing concentration of $(NH_3 + NH_4Cl)$ (curves 3 and 4). But the waves become distorted when the concentration

of $(\text{NH}_3 + \text{NH}_4\text{Cl})$ is increased beyond $1.5 M$ (curve 5). The best conditions are obtained with a medium which is $10^{-3} M$ in CoCl_2 and 1.0 to $1.5 M$ in $(\text{NH}_3 + \text{NH}_4\text{Cl})$. The half wave potential of the Co^{2+} ion shifts to more negative values with the increasing concentration of $(\text{NH}_3 + \text{NH}_4\text{Cl})$.

Effect of MPA concentration : Figure 3 represents a set of catalytic waves obtained at different concentrations of MPA ($1.0 \times 10^{-4} M - 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) in $1.5 M$ $(\text{NH}_3 + \text{NH}_4\text{Cl})$ buffer and $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ CoCl_2 . Curve 1 was obtained with the cobaltous solution in the absence

Fig. 3. Catalytic wave of MPA in $1.5 M$ $(\text{NH}_3 + \text{NH}_4\text{Cl})$ buffer containing $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ CoCl_2 and concentration of MPA was (1) none, (2) $0.1 mM$, (3) $0.2 mM$, (4) $0.489 mM$, (5) $0.952 mM$, (6) $1.308 mM$, (7) $1.818 mM$ and (8) $3.0 mM$.

of MPA. It has been found that the height of the catalytic wave increases linearly with MPA concentration and hence it is possible to determine polarographically, the small quantities of MPA of the order of $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$. The half-wave potential of Co^{2+} was found to shift towards more positive side with the increasing concentration of MPA indicating the complexation between MPA and Co^{2+} . The shift in the half wave potential of Co^{2+} and simultaneous increase in the height of catalytic wave leads to an important conclusion that the complexation between MPA and Cobalt may be an important factor responsible for the occurrence of catalytic wave. The height of the catalytic wave has also been effected by cobalt concentration. It increases with the concentration of cobalt, but not linearly.

Effect of surface active substances : Surface active substances like gelatin, thymol, triton X-100, and methyl red have been found to influence the catalytic wave markedly. Figure 4 shows the current voltage curves of MPA and CoCl_2 , both $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, in $1.5 M$

$(\text{NH}_3 + \text{NH}_4\text{Cl})$ buffer and in the presence of various surface active substances. It is seen that the presence of 0.001% triton X-100 eliminates the maximum of cobalt wave and effects the height and reproducibility of catalytic wave (curve 1). On the other hand, no catalytic wave appeared in the presence of 0.0005% methyl red, 0.02% gelatin and 0.02% thymol, wave appeared in the presence of 0.0005% methyl red, 0.02% gelatin and 0.02% thymol,

Fig. 4. Polarographic waves of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ (MPA + Co^{2+}) in presence of some surface active substances and salts.

- Curve-1. 0.001% Triton X-100
- Curve-2. 0.02% Gelatin
- Curve-3. 0.02% Thymol
- Curve-4. 0.0005% Methyl red
- Curve-5. 0.1 M KNO_3
- Curve-6. 0.1 M KCl
- Curve-7. 0.1 M Ammonium Sulphate.

although the cobalt maximum was suppressed (curves 2 and 4). However, in the presence of 0.01% thymol, a small catalytic wave appeared (curve 3). The maximum suppressors also effect the half wave potential of cobaltous ion.

It has also been noted that the presence of salts interferes with the catalytic wave (figure 4). KNO_3 in 0.1M concentration eliminates the catalytic wave (curve 5) and addition of 0.1M ammonium sulphate and 0.1M KCl reduce the catalytic wave to certain extent (curves 6 and 7).

Current voltage curves of the solution containing MPA and CoCl_2 , both $10^{-3}M$, in 1.5M $(\text{NH}_3 + \text{NH}_4\text{Cl})$ at different heights of mercury column were also recorded. It was found that the height of the catalytic wave is independent of the Hg-pressure, which is in agreement with the fact that typical kinetic currents are not diffusion controlled and the height of such waves are independent of the height of the mercury in the reservoir. On the other hand the cobalt wave is diffusion controlled.

It is apparent from the preceding studies that the wave produced by MPA in ammoniacal cobalt solution is a typical one, the half wave potential of which corresponds neither to Co^{2+} nor to MPA wave. The origin and mechanism of the electrode process associated with the catalytic wave may be explained on the basis of the complex formation between MPA and Co^{2+} (indicated by the shift in the half wave potential of Co^{2+} with the increasing concentration of MPA) in accordance with the following equation.

The coordinate bond between cobalt and the sulphhydryl group activates the bond between sulphur and hydrogen in the $-\text{SH}$ group and the deposition of hydrogen at d.m.e. is facilitated. The increase of the height of the catalytic wave and the shift of half wave potential of Co^{2+} wave is in agreement with the above statement; since, the greater the complexation, the greater will be the liberation of hydrogen ions from $-\text{SH}$ group and hence more hydrogen ion will reduce at the d.m.e. resulting in the increase in catalytic wave height.

The solution containing MPA and Co^{2+} ($1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$) in $1.5M$ ($\text{NH}_3 + \text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$) left for air oxidation was also polarographed and found to yield no catalytic wave (Fig. 1, curve 5). The difference between the behaviour of divalent and trivalent cobalt solution may be explained by the difference in their ability to form catalytically active chelate. In presence of the Co^{3+} the only reaction which may occur (leading to the formation of cobaltous complex) is between the catalytically active substance and the divalent cobalt on the surface of the electrode. The reaction between MPA and the divalent cobalt formed in this way might be very slow and therefore no catalytic wave occurred. The results achieved from the preceding study are in general accordance with the mechanism proposed by Brdicka¹³ on cobalt catalysed hydrogen waves. The presence of Co^{2+} ion in the solution is a very important factor in the marked increase in the catalytic activity of sulphur containing substances. The stable complex of cobalt with sulphur containing ligands is so stable that it hardly precipitates in an electrochemical reaction which gives a deposit of cobalt, but mainly causes catalytic hydrogen evolution.

Apparently MPA behaves typically at d.m.e. in ammoniacal cobalt solution and produces a catalytic wave which can be successfully utilised for the determination of small quantities of MPA of the order of $1.0 \times 10^{-4}M$. The wave has been found to be influenced by the concentration of buffer constituents and also by the presence of surface active substances and salts.

Our thanks are due to Dr. M. L. Mittal for helpful discussions and to Principal R. M. Advani for providing research facilities.

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Received November 8, 1968
Revised MSS received December 30, 1969

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